

THE UNIVERSITY OF ZAMBIA

SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING

**A COMPARATIVE LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF ETHANOL BLENDED FUEL AND
PETROL AS TRANSPORT FUELS IN ZAMBIA**

BY:

JAMES MWAKOI

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JAMES MWAKOI

**“Report submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the Degree of
Bachelor of Engineering in Agricultural Engineering**

2022

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this project is solely my work. Where materials from other sources were used, citations were put, with references at the end of the report.

This project is submitted in partial fulfilment of the academic requirements for the attainment of a Bachelors of Engineering degree at the University of Zambia. To the best of my knowledge, the information contained herein has not been submitted to any –other institution of learning for the award of any academic qualification.

Submitted by:

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Signed.....

15/11/2022

Date.....

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION	iv
List of Figures	viii
List of Tables	x
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	viii
ABSTRACT	xi
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	1
BACKGROUND	1
PROBLEM STATEMENT	4
OBJECTIVES	4
RATIONALE	5
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	6
LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT	6
CASSAVA BASED ETHANOL LCA	8
CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY AND MATERIALS	12
LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT	12
INVENTORY	16
IMPACT ASSESSMENT	24
INTERPRETATION	25
CHAPTER 4: RESULTS	26
EMISSIONS	26
GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL	30
CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION	34
COMPARISON OF E10 TO PETROL	34
BENEFITS OF REDUCING GREENHOUSE GASES	35
CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION	37
CONCLUSION	37
RECOMMENDATIONS	38
CHAPTER 7: REFERENCES	39
CHAPTER 8: APPENDICES	41

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1 Zambia fuel supply Chain.....	2
Figure 2.1 System boundary of the cassava-based E10/E85 fuel life cycle (base case)	8
Figure 2.2 System Boundaries of Ethanol production from Cassava.....	10
Figure 3.1 Life Cycle Assessment Structure.....	12
Figure 3.2 Bioethanol Life Cycle	14
Figure 3.3 Petrol Life Cycle	15
Figure 3.4 Showing distance between bio-ethanol plant and refinery.....	19
Figure 3.5 Showing distance between port of Beria and distribution point.....	20
Figure 4.1 Showing comparison of emissions between E10 and Petrol	29
Figure 4.2 Showing GWP comparison between E10 and Petrol.....	33

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.1: Bio-ethanol Inventory	22
Table 3.2 Petrol Inventory	23
Table 4.1 Summary of emissions from E10 life cycle	27
Table 4.2 Summary of emissions from petrol life cycle.....	28
Table 4.3 Results of comparison of emissions between E10 and petrol	29
Table 4.4 Summary of Global Warming Potential of E10.....	31
Table 4.5 Summary of Global Warming Potential of petrol.....	32
Table 4.6 Showing comparison of Global Warming Potential of E10 and Petrol	33

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

FAO Food and Agriculture Organization

E10 Fuel blend composed of 10% ethanol and 90% petrol

LCA Life Cycle Assessment

TAZAMA Tanzania Zambia Mafuta Pipelines Limited

GDP Gross Domestic Product

OMC Oil Marketing Company

GHG Greenhouse gases

CO₂ Carbon dioxide

CH₄ Methane

N₂O Nitrous oxide

GWP Global Warming Potential

ABSTRACT

The necessity of greater independency from imported crude oil has resulted in the search and formation of blended fuels as alternative transport fuels. One such blend that has received great attention worldwide (Zambia included) is the blend between Ethanol and Petrol. Zambia has adopted a blend commonly known as E10 (10% Ethanol blended with 90% Petrol) as the blend has proved to be economically viable when compared to fossil fuels. However, the environmental impacts associated with this blend have not been assessed here in Zambia.

Therefore, this study ascertained whether E10 has a better environmental performance as compared to petrol in its use as a transport fuel in Zambia. A standard procedure known as a Life Cycle Assessment was used to carry out this comparison. The impact category selected was the Global Warming Potential, the functional unit used to compare the life cycles of E10 and petrol was 1 litre of E10 equivalent consumed by a new passenger car to travel a specific distance (13.1km for E10 and 13.46km for petrol).

The results obtained from this study show that E10 throughout its life cycle reduces environmental loads as it produced less emissions as compared to petrol. E10 has a 3.59% reduction in global warming potential when compared to gasoline. These results are of importance as they can affirm Zambia's validity to trade carbon credits on the international carbon trading exchange market.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

The chapter discusses the background of the research. It defines the problems relating to the project, the scope of the study, objectives, and the rationale of the study.

1.1 BACKGROUND

1.1.1 Zambian Transport Sector

Zambia's transport sector plays a critical role in the growth and development of the country's economy. Road transport is considered the most popular and most common mode of transport in the country (Mtonga, 1990). Its contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth has averaged 3.2 percent in recent years (Mulungu & Ng'ombe, 2017). Road transport facilitates growth in value added to agriculture, trade, commerce, mining, and tourism, accounting for over 60 percent of the cost of producing goods and commodities. As an essential input, road transport costs translate into the competitiveness of all goods produced in the country and, therefore has a significant bearing on the welfare of the people (Mulungu & Ng'ombe, 2017).

One of the most common fuels used in the Zambian Transport sector is a fossil fuel known as petrol which is made when crude oil is broken down into various products by fractional distillation to produce a transparent, petroleum-derived flammable liquid that is used primarily as a fuel in most spark-ignited internal combustion engines (The International Council On Clean Transportation, 2011).

Zambia's total petroleum requirements are met through imports as the country has not recorded proven reserves of crude oil. As shown in Figure 1.1, Zambia imports a mixed petroleum feedstock consisting of crude oil, Naphtha and Diesel from the middle east, which is shipped to Tanzania and pumped over a distance of 1710 km to Zambia (Ndola) by the TAZAMA pipeline. The fuel is then refined at INDENI Refinery and stored at the Ndola Fuel Terminal where the fuel is sold to privately owned Oil Marketing Companies (OMCs) who distribute the fuel locally (Energy Regulation Board, 2020). However as of the year 2022 already refined petrol is shipped from the middle east to Oil Marketing Companies who transport the fuel from the port of beria in

Mozambique to Zambia by means of tanker trucks, the petrol is then distributed throughout the country by road.

Figure 1:1 Zambia fuel Supply Chain

1.1.2 Biofuels Production

Zambia is currently faced with competing strategic objectives related to energy: economic sustainability, diminishing oil supplies, and concerns regarding global climate change. The transportation sector is at the crux of this dilemma, as a result bio fuels are being tested and promoted as alternatives to overcome the challenges mentioned above (Keifer & Effenberger, 2019).

Biofuels are fuels that are produced from biomass sources through a variety of biological, thermal, and chemical processes, as such they are classified as renewable fuels, unlike petroleum which is a fossil fuel produced from crude oil (Hassan & Kalam, 2013). Biofuels are generally considered nontoxic and have been gaining increased public and scientific attention, driven by factors such as oil price spikes and greenhouse gas emissions from fossil fuels (South African Agency for Science and Technology Advancement, 2009).

One such biofuel is bioethanol, which is a liquid fuel produced through the fermentation of several different types of feedstocks such as cassava, corn, wood etc. Bio-fuels hold the promise of sustainable and environmentally friendly energy forms and consequently, global production increased by 8% from the levels in 2005 to 33 thousand million litres in 2009. It has been

established that the production of bioethanol and other domestic forms of energy is economically viable and feasible with available technologies (Nuwamanya & Chiwona-karlun, 2012).

In this study bioethanol obtained from cassava will be of interest. The choice of this feedstock is based on availability and cost. The high productivity and yield of cassava along with its ability to grow on marginal soils, requiring a minimum amount of labour and management costs, have placed it among the top candidates for bio-ethanol production in Zambia (Nuwamanya & Chiwona-karlun, 2012). As a result, Zambia has in the recent past supported the production of bioethanol from cassava as a feedstock and is in the process of commercializing the blending of bioethanol with petrol to be used as a transport fuel. The blending ratios approved are 10% of Ethanol and 90% of Petrol to form a blend commonly known as E10 (Keifer & Effenberger, 2019).

1.1.3 Cassava as a bioethanol feedstock

In Zambia, cassava is produced mainly by small-scale farmers. The majority of cassava producers are in Northern, Luapula and North-Western provinces producing 210,706 tonnes, 157,885 tonnes and 74,618 tonnes respectively. These account for about 78.8% of all producers in Zambia (Chikoti, 2019). Cassava cultivation has tripled in recent years, from 360,000 tonnes in 1985 to 1,114,000 tonnes in 2013 (Chikoti, 2019). The increase in cassava cultivation is largely attributed to the withdrawal of maize subsidies. Since 2005, the country has produced more than 1 million tonnes of cassava annually. Cassava yields vary between producers using traditional cassava cultivars (1 tonnes/ha) and improved cultivars (2–3.5 tonnes/ha). Cassava has the potential to yield as high as 20–40 tonnes/ha. Yields in Zambia average 5.8 tonnes/ha compared with the African average of 8.4 tonnes/ha (Chikoti, 2019).

Demand for cassava for both human and industrial consumption has also grown in the urban and industrial centres of Lusaka and Copperbelt provinces (Poole, 2010).

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The development and production of bioethanol to be blended with petrol is currently being promoted locally by the Ministry of Energy. The Zambian government views the use of bioethanol in the transportation sector as an important strategy for reducing the petroleum import bill, while contributing to energy diversification and security. To support its production, in 2009 blending ratios for bio-ethanol were set at 10%. This entails mixing 90% petrol with 10% Bioethanol. The resulting blended fuel is referred to as Ethanol blended fuel (E10).

Because of the renewable bioethanol content in E10, it is frequently regarded to be more environmentally sustainable than petrol. However, its environmental performance has not yet been assessed. Thus, the need for a life cycle assessment to get a complete picture of such potential benefits.

1.3 OBJECTIVES

General Objectives;

This research project aims to assess the environmental performance of using ethanol blended fuel obtained from cassava and petrol as a transport fuel compared to petrol.

Specific Objectives;

- i. To characterize the cassava and ethanol production processes in Zambia.
- ii. To quantify the life cycle Greenhouse gas emissions associated with the use of E10 and petrol as a transport fuel in Zambia.
- iii. To characterize Global Warming Potential of E10 and petrol.

1.4 RATIONALE

The national consumption of petroleum increased by 10.2% from 1,329,290.66 metric tonnes in 2020 to 1,464,822.66 metric tonnes in 2021 (Sanders, 2011). Crude oil prices also increased in 2021 owing to the growing global demand that outstripped supply, this was driven by the ever-increasing global demand for crude oil (Sanders, 2011). The Zambian government views biofuels as a means to reducing the petroleum import bill, while contributing to energy diversification and security (Bioenergy, 2020). Bio-fuels when burned generally produce fewer emissions resulting in the reduction of greenhouse gases thereby reducing global warming.

The National Energy policy 2019 included policy measures for the blending of biofuels. To support production, in 2009 blending ratios for ethanol were set at 10 percent. The same blending ratios are mentioned in the National determined contributions to be achieved by 2030 (Bioenergy, 2020).

The results from this study will help Zambia grade its progress towards the reduction of global emissions, thereby affirming Zambia's validation to trade carbon credits on the international carbon credit market.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter gives a review of some literature in order to understand how different assessments relating to ethanol and petrol have been carried out, what methods were used to assess the environmental performance of ethanol and petrol, how the life cycle Greenhouse gas emissions were quantified and lastly the advantages and disadvantages of each method were discussed.

2.1 Life Cycle Assessment

The concept of conducting a detailed examination of the life cycle of a product or process with the aim of increasing environmental awareness on the part of the general public, industry and government has been coined as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) (Jensen et al., 1997). The LCA technique assesses the environmental impacts associated with all the stages of a product's life. The most important applications are the analysis of the contribution of the life cycle stages to the overall environmental load, usually with the aim of prioritising improvements on products or processes as well as comparison between products for internal use (Jensen et al., 1997). A life cycle assessment can be conducted using three approaches: the first being Cradle-to-gate which assess a product from the point of its extraction to the point of its use. The second approach is Gate-to-gate which assess a product from a point along its life cycle to another point within the cycle. The third is the Cradle-to-grave, analysis of a product under this approach is done from the point the product is extracted to the point of its disposal (Jensen et al., 1997). An LCA study consists of four main stages, these are explained below.

2.1.1 Goal and Scope;

The first stage is the goal and scope which ensures that the LCA is performed consistently, it highlights functional units, system boundaries and limits of the analysis that are set to outline where in the life cycle the study begins and where it ends, and to identify what processes within the system will be assessed. A functional unit is the basis for the study, it is a measurement of production or output against which impact indicator metrics are normalized. The scope of an LCA is determined by the number of life cycle stages and impact categories that will be assessed. One assessment might take one impact, making it very targeted and focused while another might choose a more comprehensive approach, addressing many categories (Jensen et al., 1997).

2.1.2 Inventory;

The next step is setting up an inventory, this is a collection of data. The inventory includes things like emissions, energy requirements and material flow for each process involved. These are flows into and out of the system being studied. The data of these are adjusted depending on the functional unit being considered. At the end of this phase, an inventory list is created that details data for the system under study (Jensen et al., 1997).

2.1.3 Impact Assessment;

Under this phase, evaluation of inventory data is done in order to make it meaningful in context of potential damage to the environment or human health. This phase therefore translates measurements into information for expressing their impact. Raw data is characterized to communicate the relative potency of materials, emissions or other factors (Jensen et al., 1997).

2.1.4 Interpretation;

Under the final phase results are analysed in context of the goal and scope of the study set out at the beginning, conclusions are then checked and verified (Jensen et al., 1997).

2.2 Cassava Based Ethanol LCA

A Cradle-to-grave analysis was conducted for cassava-based ethanol fuel in Thailand. The aim of the analysis was to assess the potentials of E10 for promoting energy security and reducing environmental impacts in comparison with conventional gasoline (Nguyen & Gheewala, 2008).

In Thailand, the E10 blend was the first stage of the government ethanol policy which was to be followed by higher blends, e.g., E20, E85. The method used for this study was the standard Life Cycle Assessment.

In their study, the functional unit (FU) chosen to compare the life cycle energy and environmental performance of E10 and gasoline was one litre of gasoline equivalent consumed by a new passenger car to travel a specific distance. A new passenger car runs around 13.46 km per litre of gasoline, whereas it runs 13.31 km per litre of E10. The comparison in vehicle fuel economy revealed that 1 L of E10 was equal to 0.989 L of gasoline. The system boundary chosen for this study is shown in the diagram below.

Figure 2.1: System boundary of the cassava-based E10/E85 fuel life cycle (base case)(Nguyen & Gheewala, 2008)

As shown in Fig. 2.1 the four main unit processes of the cassava- based E10 fuel system for the life cycle inventory (LCI) were cassava production, ethanol conversion, transportation and fuel combustion in vehicles. The system boundary also includes various sub-processes associated with the four main processes, agrochemical manufacturing, crude oil extraction/refining, electricity production and solar energy capturing.

The results obtained showed that Ethanol in the form of E10, along its whole life cycle, reduced certain environmental loads as compared to gasoline. The percentage reductions relative to gasoline were 6.1% for fossil energy use, 6.0% for global warming potential, 6.8% for acidification, and 12.2% for nutrient enrichment (Nguyen & Gheewala, 2008).

Another similar study was conducted on the same feed stock (Cassava) in Colombia, the Colombian government included one law in 2001(Law 693), with the rules for the use of bioethanol, and the economic incentives for production, commercialization and consumption. In 2003, the Colombian government resolutions included a blend of 10% for bioethanol with petrol in combustion for cars. The Methodology used in this study was the Life Cycle Assessment methodology based on the ISO 1404's framework. The steps that the study adopted are: goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment and interpretation of the results (Naranjo & Ambientales, 2014).

The objective of this study was to assess the commercial bioethanol production from cassava for Colombia, based on a life-cycle approach. The functional unit (FU) of this study was 1 L of 99.5% bioethanol production from cassava as an octane improvement fuel (Naranjo & Ambientales, 2014).

However, it was necessary to evaluate the environmental impacts in the overall life cycle assessment of the product, as well as determine the fossil fuels intensity for ethanol production, the carbon footprint of bioethanol from cassava and other impacts according to the Colombian conditions. This was due to variations in displaying findings from other LCA studies developed, caused by different input data on crops, farm energy, different conversion in ethanol technology and co products energy credits (Naranjo & Ambientales, 2014).

Figure 2.2: System Boundaries of Ethanol production from Cassava (Naranjo & Ambientales, 2014)

For this study, farm production data were collected as primary data by surveys to farmers in Urabá, Colombia (PROTRACOY), and the Antioquia's Agriculture Secretary. This data included land preparation, cassava plantation and cassava harvest. Secondary data used in this study come from literature (Naranjo & Ambientales, 2014).

The inventory data (primary and secondary) of each step were introduced in SimaPro v7.22, to evaluate the environmental impacts using a CML 2000 method for eutrophication, acidification, photochemical oxidation, human toxicity, ozone layer depletion and abiotic depletion (Naranjo & Ambientales, 2014).

The results from the study showed that the carbon footprint of cassava ethanol is 0.395kg CO₂e per kg of ethanol. This means 75 g CO₂eq/ MJ allowed a net reduction of 13.5 g CO₂ e/MJ GHG emissions as compared to conventional gasoline (Naranjo & Ambientales, 2014).

The study concluded that the carbon footprint of cassava ethanol is lower than fossil fuels, with a 20% lower footprint (Naranjo & Ambientales, 2014).

The LCA used in this study is a cradle-to-grate life cycle assessment (LCA) focused on the climate change impact category and performed in accordance with the standard methods of the ISO 14040 framework, which is carried out in four distinct phases; (i) goal and scope definition, (ii) life cycle inventory analysis, (iii) life cycle impact assessment, and (IV) Interpretation.

3.1.1 Goal and Scope

The goal of this study is to compare the environmental impact of the use of E10 (10% Ethanol and 90% Petrol) and petrol as a transport fuel compared to Petrol.

The functional unit chosen to compare the life cycle environmental performance of petrol and E10 is 1 litre of E10 equivalent consumed by a new passenger car to travel a specific distance. Adopted from a study by Nguyen & Gheewala (2008), fuel economy used in this study was 1L of E10 is equal to 0.989L of petrol. Thus, a car using E10 as a fuel will consume 1L of E10 over a distance of 13.31km while a car using petrol as a fuel will consume 1L of petrol over a distance of 13.46km (Nguyen & Gheewala, 2008).

3.1.2 System Boundary

The system boundary for this study (Figure 3.2) shows the relevant steps and processes taken for the production of ethanol and the blending of ethanol with petrol, beginning from the agricultural aspect of the feedstock cultivation to the production of ethanol and the blending of ethanol with petrol to produce E10.

Agricultural inputs include; Fertilizers, herbicides, lime and nitrogen. Field practices include all activities that take place on the farm during the production of cassava such as tillage, land preparation and harvest. Lastly ethanol production includes milling, hydrolysis, fermentation, distillation and dehydration. (Figure 3.2)

Figure 3.2: Bioethanol Life Cycle

Figure 3.3 Petrol Life Cycle

3.1.3 Impact Category studied

Global Warming Potential has been selected to be relevant to the analysis of the environmental burdens of this life cycle and was investigated. Impact categories that are global in nature, i.e. emissions occurring outside the geographical area of the production sites as a result of activities occurring within the system boundary, were also included under the Global Warming Potential.

3.1.4 Data Quality

The data used in the study was based on the current cassava production profile in Zambia. Average data values over a seasonal ethanol production period, and corresponding cassava processing season's data were considered sufficient to meet the goals of the study, this approach was used for the initial consideration of the variability of process parameters used in the analysis.

3.2 INVENTORY

This section provides a general identification and grouping of the sub-systems of the cradle-to-gate life-cycle. The materials used are listed in this section. Each of the sub-processes of the life cycle were then described with respect to its function, and the approach used to gather the relevant data is also outlined under each sub-section.

In line with the definition of the system, it was considered useful to group the sub-processes into those over which the company has a significant degree of control (termed “core” processes, and those over which the company has little control (“sub” processes).

Microsoft Excel was one of the tools used to conduct this research study it was used to arrange and compute data with a high level of accuracy, using this tool emissions and Global Warming Potential were computed. In addition, GHG emission factor set 2022 was an application used to access the latest emission factors of GHG’s as well as convert them to the desired unit of volume, mass or energy. Using this tool, latest emission factors as agreed by the international community at the COP26 conference were accessed. Lastly, Google Earth Pro was used to carry out visualization and assessment of geographical data, using this tool distances between locations were estimated.

3.2.1 Core Processes

These are the processes that are directly related to the sites of production of bio-ethanol, and are directly associated with the processing of the product. These are:

- Crude Oil Extraction
- Cassava Cultivation

- Cassava Processing (Milling)
- Ethanol Processing
- Refinery Process
- Road Transportation

The unit processes involved in each subsystem are described in this section, together with the details of the approach that was used to gather and compile the data relevant to each unit. Where bound by confidentiality of the processing details, a generic description of the technology was employed. The corresponding flows that are also sensitive remained "masked" in the inventory, but their associated environmental burdens were accounted for, in full.

Crude Oil Extraction;

This process involves the drilling of oil from beneath the earth's surface. The oil is then pumped and transported to the refinery. Data collected includes the amount of water used during the extraction process as well as the quantity of crude oil extracted.

Cassava Cultivation;

This is the process that involves the growing of Cassava, including processes such as land preparation, planting, fertilizing, weeding, irrigation if applicable and harvesting. Data collected includes cassava yield per hectare, size of fields, methods of cultivation and fertiliser use per hectare.

The location of cassava production used for this study was assumed to be Northern Province as data obtained from Zambia Agricultural Research Institute shows that Northern province has the highest number of cassava producers, favourable climatic and soil conditions that favour cassava production, as well as a high resistance to disease resulting in an average yield of 14.5ton per hectare.

The cassava production fields were assumed to cover an area of about 20,000Ha.

Cassava Processing;

This is the process where cassava is sorted cleaned and then chopped and dried. Data that was to be collected includes the location of processing. The location of this process was assumed to be the ethanol processing plant, which is assumed to be surrounded by the cassava fields.

Ethanol Production;

his process involves the crushing, mixing, liquefaction, fermentation, distillation and dehydration of the cassava to produce ethanol. Data that was to be collected includes the location of ethanol production plant as well as the quantities of steam and electricity used in the production process. The Ethanol processing plant is assumed to be located around the cassava fields which are located in Northern Province.

Petrol Refining Process;

This process involves the separation of constituents from crude oil, the conversion of crude oil to petrol and the treatment of petrol. Data collected includes the quantities of steam and electricity used in the refinery process.

Refinery Process;

This stage involves the Blending of Petrol and Ethanol to form E10. Data that was to be collected includes the location of the refinery and blending ratios used.

With regards the refinery process it was assumed that the location of the refinery plant was assumed to be INDENI Oil Refinery and blending takes place at the refinery in a ratio of 1:10 (10% ethanol and 90% petrol)

Transportation;

There were several transport stages involved in this life-cycle study. In principle, all transportation process was included in the assessment. However, the following three steps of transportation that are directly involved with the manufacture of the product were considered in this study:

- Transportation of cassava from fields to the Ethanol Processing Plant, it was assumed that 7ton diesel operated trucks are used to transport cassava from the surrounding fields to the bio-ethanol processing plant.

- Transportation of Ethanol from the Plant to the Refinery, it was assumed that the ethanol was to be transported by 37,000l capacity diesel operated tanker trucks that transport the ethanol from the bio-ethanol plant to the refinery (Figure).

Figure 3.4: Showing distance between bio-ethanol plant and refinery

- Transportation of petrol from the port of Beria to the distribution point, data collected indicates that petrol is transported by 37,000 diesel operated trucks from the port of beria in Mozambique to Lusaka where it is stored and distributed.

Figure 3.5: Showing distance between port of Beria and distribution point(1305km)

Based on the distance and load capacities involved, it was assumed that they are the most intensive of the transport steps involved and would hence be the ones of most significance.

Fuel usage/combustion:

This process relates to the amount of fuel (litres) combusted per kilometre driven, data collected involves consumption per litre of a new passenger car used E10 and petrol as a fuel respectively. A car using E10 as a fuel will consume 1L of E10 over a distance of 13.31km while a car using petrol as a fuel will consume 1L of petrol over a distance of 13.46km (Nguyen & Gheewala, 2008).

3.2.2 Sub Processes

These are processes that involve the production of the ancillary flows of utilities and reagents that are used in the foreground sub-process. It was considered sufficient to model these processes using

relevant published information, due to the inaccessibility of local primary data relating to them and the low degree of influence on the environmental impacts.

These background sub-processes are:

- Electricity production
- Steam production
- Fertiliser production

Table 3.1 shows a summary of the data that was required for analysis of each stage of the cycle as well as where the needed data was be collected from. The table below also highlights the methods to be used so as to obtain the needful data

Table 3.1: Bio-ethanol inventory

Main Process	Data Collected	Data Source	Collecting Method
Cassava Production	Fuel use = Manual Labor Fertilizer use = 0.0046N-0.0024P- 0.00452K (kg) Herbicide use = Manual weeding	Zambia Agricultural Research Institute	Interviews
Transportation	Distance: (7km + 745km) = 752km Transport Mode = Diesel Tipper Trucks,	Ministry of Energy, Dept of Petroleum	Interviews
Ethanol Conversion	Process steam =0.2843kwh Electricity = 0.11826kwh	Institute for Local Self-Reliance (Lorenz et al., 2007)	Report
Refinery	Ethanol = 0.11 Petrol = 0.9l	Ministry of Energy, Dept of Petroleum	Interviews
Fuel usage/ Combustion	Distance: 1km = 13.31km Vehicle = New passenger Car	(Nguyen & Gheewala, 2008)	Report

Table 3.2: Petrol Inventory

Main Process	Data Collected	Data Source	Collecting Method
Crude Oil Extraction	Water = 0.001029895kg Crude oil = 0.16813L	Al-Daura Oil Refinery, Middle East (Alanbari et al., 2016)	Report
Refinery	Electricity = 0.015104106 kwh Steam = 0.428035244kg	Al-Daura Oil Refinery, Middle East (Alanbari et al., 2016)	Report
Transportation	Distance = 1305km Transport Mode = Diesel Tanker Trucks	Ministry of Energy, Dept of Petroleum	Interviews
Fuel usage/ Combustion	Distance: 1km = 13.46km Vehicle = New Passenger car	(Nguyen & Gheewala, 2008)	Report

3.3 IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Under this section, data from the inventory were assessed, the indicator results of the impact category were detailed in this step, the impacts were also measured at this stage. As further elaborated below, quantitative calculations that use activity data and emissions factors were used to estimate greenhouse gas emissions. Activity data is a measure of level of activity that results in GHG emissions, such data may consist of litres of fuel or electricity consumed. Emission factors reflect the average GHG intensity per unit of activity data per given source.

Calculating emissions from GHG sources generally involves the following six steps:

1. Determining consumption of each consumption combusted fuel or energy consumption.
2. Determining the CO₂ emission factor for each fuel or unit of energy consumed.
3. Determining CH₄ and N₂O emission factors for each fuel or unit of energy consumed.
4. Calculation of CO₂ emissions by multiplying the emission factor by fuel or energy consumption.
5. Calculation of CH₄ and N₂O emissions by multiplying emission factors by fuel or energy consumption.
6. Conversion of CH₄ and N₂O emissions to CO₂e.

(Jensen et al., 1997)

Quantitative analysis:

$$E = A \times EF \dots\dots\dots (Eqn 1)$$

Where:

E = Emissions in kg CO₂ equivalent

A = Activity data (mass, volume or energy unit)

EF = Emission factor in kg CO₂ equivalent per mass, volume or energy unit.

3.4 INTERPRETATION

This phase takes place throughout the first three stages. However, results were validated by indicating significant impacts, conclusions, limitations and recommendations were then given.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

This chapter outlines the data collected to quantify the emissions of this research project, it also shows the results obtained from the quantification of emissions of E10 and petrol as transport fuels in Zambia. All values were adjusted as per functional unit.

4.3 EMISSIONS

This section outlines results of emissions from the environmental performance conducted on E10 and Petrol as per functional unit. Table 4.1 outlines estimates of gas emissions produced from the life cycle of E10 as per functional unit, presented as contributions from main processes. Emissions estimates produced from the life cycle of Petrol are presented in the same format (Table 4.2) as per functional unit to facilitate comparison.

Table 4.1: Summary of emissions from E10 life cycle

Main Process	Emissions (kg)		
	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O
Crude-Oil Extraction			
(Water)	1.584x10 ⁻⁴	1.0215x10 ⁻⁶	5.427x10 ⁻⁷
(Crude Oil)	4.1589x10 ⁻¹	1.6524x10 ⁻⁵	3.2328x10 ⁻⁶
Refinery			
(Electricity)	2.628x10 ⁻³	1.0989x10 ⁻⁵	1.8828x10 ⁻⁵
(Steam)	6.584x10 ⁻²	4.2453x10 ⁻⁴	2.259x10 ⁻⁴
Transportation			
(Cassava Production)	2.661x10 ⁻⁴	2.6x10 ⁻⁸	3.72x10 ⁻⁶
(Ethanol)	2.036x10 ⁻³	1.98x10 ⁻⁷	2.846x10 ⁻⁵
(Petrol)	3.2094x10 ⁻²	3.1356x10 ⁻⁶	4.4865x10 ⁻⁴
Ethanol Conversion			
(Process Steam)	3.435x10 ⁻²	2.221x10 ⁻⁴	1.178x10 ⁻⁴
(Electricity)	1.434x10 ⁻²	6.0x10 ⁻⁴	1.027x10 ⁻⁴
Fuel-Usage/ Combustion (1L)	2.2443	6.59037x10 ⁻³	6.0392x10 ⁻³
Total	2.8119025	7.8688941x10 ⁻³	6.9890335x10 ⁻³

Table 4.2: Summary of emissions from petrol life cycle

Main Process	Emissions (kg)		
	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O
Crude-Oil Extraction			
(Water)	1.7411×10^{-4}	1.1220×10^{-6}	5.9700×10^{-7}
(Crude Oil)	4.5703×10^{-1}	1.8162×10^{-5}	3.5530×10^{-6}
Refinery			
(Electricity)	2.8880×10^{-3}	1.2083×10^{-5}	2.0692×10^{-5}
(Steam)	7.2363×10^{-2}	4.6655×10^{-4}	2.4826×10^{-4}
Transportation			
	3.5276×10^{-2}	3.4463×10^{-6}	4.9309×10^{-4}
Fuel-Usage/ Combustion (0.989L)	2.3000	7.2394×10^{-3}	6.636×10^{-3}
Total	2.867731110	7.740×10^{-3}	7.4021×10^{-3}

The emissions from the life cycles of E10 and petrol were compared and the results as a percentage difference are listed in table 4.3, a negative denotes a reduction while positive denotes an increase with regards to emission percentage difference. Figure 4.1 shows the comparison as a representation weight.

Table 4.3: Results from comparison of emissions between E10 and Petrol.

Emissions(kg)	Petrol	E10	Percentage
CO ₂	2.867731110	2.8119025	-1.95%
CH ₄	7.740x10 ⁻³	7.8688941x10 ⁻³	+1.64%
N ₂ O	7.4021x10 ⁻³	6.9890335x10 ⁻³	-5.58%

Figure 4.1: Showing comparison of emissions between E10 and Petrol

4.4 GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL

This section outlines results of the impact category being assessed in this study. Table 4.4 outlines results of Global Warming Potential presented as a breakdown of main processes of E10 life cycle, while table 4.5 outlines results of Global Warming Potential of Petrol.

Table 4.4: Summary of Global Warming Potential of E10

Main Process	GWP (kg CO ₂ -eq)		
	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O
Crude-Oil Extraction			
(Water)	1.58445x10 ⁻⁴	2.55384x10 ⁻⁵	1.61982x10 ⁻⁴
(Crude Oil)	4.1589x10 ⁻¹	4.1319x10 ⁻⁴	9.6345x10 ⁻⁴
Refinery			
(Electricity)	2.628x10 ⁻³	2.74896x10 ⁻⁴	5.61105x10 ⁻³
(Steam)	6.5851x10 ⁻²	1.06137x10 ⁻²	6.73272x10 ⁻²
Transportation			
(Cassava Production)	2.661x10 ⁻⁴	6.5x10 ⁻⁷	1.108x10 ⁻³
(Ethanol)	2.036x10 ⁻³	4.972x10 ⁻⁶	8.481x10 ⁻³
(Petrol)	3.2094x10 ⁻²	7.8390x10 ⁻⁵	1.33686x10 ⁻¹
Ethanol Conversion			
(Process Steam)	3.435x10 ⁻²	5.537x10 ⁻⁴	3.512x10 ⁻²
(Electricity)	1.434x10 ⁻²	1.5x10 ⁻²	3.061x10 ⁻²
Fuel-Usage/ Combustion (1L)	2.244903	1.6475943x10 ⁻¹	1.7996286
Total	2.812516545	1.917244664x10 ⁻¹	2.082697282

Table 4.5: Summary of Global Warming Potential of petrol

Main Process	GWP (kg CO₂-eq)		
	CO₂	CH₄	N₂O
Crude-Oil Extraction			
(Water)	1.7411x10 ⁻⁴	2.8064x10 ⁻⁵	1.780x10 ⁻⁴
(Crude Oil)	4.5703x10 ⁻¹	4.5405x10 ⁻⁴	1.058x10 ⁻²
Refinery			
(Electricity)	2.8880x10 ⁻³	3.0208x10 ⁻⁴	6.1664x10 ⁻³
(Steam)	7.2363x10 ⁻²	1.1663x10 ⁻²	7.3981x10 ⁻²
Transportation	3.5276x10 ⁻²	8.6159x10 ⁻⁵	1.4694x10 ⁻¹
Fuel-Usage/ Combustion (0.989L)	2.3000	1.8098x10 ⁻¹	1.9775
Total	2.867731110	1.9351335x10 ⁻¹	2.215345400

The Global Warming Potential results from the life cycles of E10 and petrol were compared and are presented as a percentage difference in table 4.6, a negative denotes a reduction while positive denotes an increase with regards to emission percentage difference while figure 4.2 shows the comparison as a representation of main processes. GWP conversion factors are listed at A2.

Table 4.6 Showing comparison of Global Warming Potential of E10 and Petrol

(kg CO ₂ -eq)	PETROL	E10	PERCENTAGE
CO ₂	2.867731110	2.812516545	-1.93%
CH ₄	1.935135x10 ⁻¹	0.191724466	-0.924%
N ₂ O	2.2153454	2.082697282	-5.98%
TOTAL	5.276590010	5.086938293	-3.594%

Figure 4.2: Showing GWP comparison between E10 and Petrol

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

This Chapter discusses the key findings from the previous chapter (results), as well as the correlation between findings and compares them to those in literature review.

5.1 Comparison of E10 to Petrol

The emissions assessed under this study in relation to the Global Warming Potential were carbon dioxide, methane and Nitrous oxide as these gases are emitted throughout the life cycles of both E10 and Petrol, therefore, providing a basis for comparison between the two fuels.

The findings from this study (figure 4.1) showed that for both fuels carbon dioxide contributed the largest amount of emissions as compared to methane and nitrous oxide, with the largest contributing process being the Fuel usage/combustion stage. This is due to the fact that Petrol is composed of hydrocarbons, which are hydrogen (H) and carbon (C) atoms that are bonded to form hydrocarbon molecules. Air on the other hand is primarily composed of nitrogen (N) and oxygen (O₂)

In this combustion reaction, we see that the hydrogen from the petrol combines with oxygen from the air to produce water (H₂O). The carbon from the fuel combines with the oxygen from the air to produce carbon dioxide (CO₂) as the end product. Thus, the process contributes fraction of emissions.

However, results from the comparison of emissions (table 4.3) showed a reduction of 1.95% in carbon dioxide emissions of E10 as compared to petrol, this is as a result of the fuel-usage/combustion process of E10 giving out a contribution 2.2443kg of CO₂ while that of petrol was 2.3kg of CO₂. This is expected as the combustion of ethanol produces less CO₂ as compared to petrol.

Comparison of methane emissions (table 4.3) showed an increase of 1.64% in emissions for E10 as compared to petrol, this increase is caused by the ethanol conversion process where ethanol is extracted from cassava, this process consists of a subprocess known as fermentation where methane is produced as a major by product, thereby, resulting in an increase of methane in the E10 life cycle as compared to petrol.

Nitrous oxide emissions were largely contributed by the fuel-usage/combustion main process in both fuel life cycles, when fuel is combusted part of the nitrogen that is in the fuel and the air gets oxidized creating nitrous oxide, however, it was noted from the comparison (table 4.3) that E10 had a decrease of 5.58% of nitrous oxide emissions as compared to petrol. This decrease was expected as the amount of petrol combusted in the E10 life cycle was less than that combusted in the petrol life cycle.

Findings from the previous chapter displayed results of Global Warming Potential as the impact category being assessed for both E10 and petrol life cycles. The units used for the assessment of Global Warming Potential was kg CO₂-eq, therefore the emissions from methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) were converted to kg CO₂-eq.

The results from the comparison (table 4.6) shows that E10 has the potential for reducing global warming when compared to petrol as it had a GWP reduction of 3.594%. This result is expected as E10 consists of 10% of ethanol, the life cycle assessment of ethanol revealed that less emissions are emitted as compared to the petrol life cycle. As in the case of the emission assessment the fuel-usage/combustion process contributes the most emissions in both cases, however the reduction in quantity of petrol in E10 results in a cleaner combustion process being the major reason as to why the Global Warming Potential was reduced.

5.2 Benefits of Reducing Greenhouse gases

The findings from this research study clearly show that using E10 reduces the amount of greenhouse gases emitted, the reduction of greenhouse gases is directly proportional to the reduction of global warming.

Emission reduction can deliver both immediate and long-term developmental outcomes, the findings from this study could affirm Zambia's validation to trade carbon credits on the international carbon exchange market, thereby reaping economic benefits. The fossil fuel global market Zambia being a part of, has been prone to unstable price fluctuations attributed to availability and brakeage's in supply chains of fossil fuels such as petrol, this volatility can be greatly reduced by using environmentally clean fuels. There by enhancing Zambia's energy security. Long term benefits could also be achieved, as reducing greenhouse gas emissions could

prevent premature deaths associated with air and respiratory diseases, thereby providing for a healthy and productive work force.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In this chapter, conclusions and recommendations drawn from the study are presented.

6.1 CONCLUSION

The overall objective of this study was to assess the environmental performance of using ethanol blended from cassava as a transport fuel compared to petrol. This was done by carrying out cradle to gate life cycle assessments of E10 and petrol, where all their respective production main processes were analysed and greenhouse gas emissions quantified. Comparisons of emissions based on the fuel's respective life cycles and main processes were then made and respective Global Warming Potential calculated and compared.

The findings obtained from this study showed that the use of E10 results in less emission of greenhouse gases as compared to petrol, however, for both fuels the fuel-usage/combustion process contributes the largest emissions as compared to other processes throughout the life cycle.

The study also revealed that the use of E10 as a fuel as compared to petrol results in a lower Global Warming Potential with a reduction of 3.594%. This reduction is mainly attributed to the 10% composition of ethanol in E10 as ethanol produces lower quantities of by and end products once combusted.

However, despite the successful completion of this study limitations have been experienced, these include the inaccessibility of data as Zambia currently only has two privately owned ethanol production plants in operation and one government partly owned ethanol plant that is still under construction, as a result locally characterized data was not available. As well as the lack of consolidated data that would be used to as parameters and feed into life cycle assessment software.

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

- A similar research project would have to be conducted however, the study should include examination of other impact categories relevant to land and water use as most agrochemical products such as fertilizers and pesticides may have a large impact on acidification, eutrophication, land-use change and carcinogens.
- A similar study should be conducted however, the comparison of fuels could be between petrol and a higher blend of Ethanol.
- A similar life cycle assessment would have to be conducted however, the research should compare the environmental performance of E10 as a transport fuel against cost or economic benefits of using the blend.
- A study that can evaluate the biofuel potential of using sugarcane residue in Zambia.

CHAPTER 8: REFERENCES

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CHAPTER 9: APPENDICES

A1 Base Calculations

1 ton of Cassava = 150L Ethanol

1 Hecate = 14.5tons of cassava (Average yield)

A2 GWP Conversion Factors (kg CO₂-eq)

CO₂ = 1

CH₄ = 25

N₂O = 298

A3 Equations

Equation 125